

**THEORETICAL-METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF THE
CONCEPT OF HISTORICAL-LOGICAL COMPETENCE****Akhmedova Kamuna Mukhammadkhodjayevna**

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competence, historical thinking, logical thinking, integrative approach, axiological approach, pedagogical technology, history education, method, tool, evaluation

ABSTRACT

This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation of historical-logical competence in future history teachers. The pedagogical essence of the concept of competence, its structural components and its role in history education are scientifically covered. Also, effective mechanisms for the development of historical thinking and logical thinking based on an integrative-modular approach are substantiated.

Introduction

The processes of globalization and informatization are placing new demands on the education system. In modern society, where knowledge rapidly becomes outdated, it is not sufficient for an individual to merely possess knowledge; rather, they must be able to analyze, process, and apply it in practice. Therefore, the competency-based approach has become a priority direction in education.

History education is no exception to this process. The primary task of history as a subject is not limited to teaching past events but also includes developing students' historical thinking, critical approach, and logical reasoning. From this perspective, the development of historical-logical competence in future history teachers is considered an actual pedagogical issue.

Literature Review And Methods

The concept of competence has been widely studied in pedagogy, and its theoretical foundations have been developed by both foreign and local scholars. In particular, A.V. Khutorskoy interprets competence as an integrative unity of knowledge, skills, and experience of an individual, while I.A. Zimnyaya considers it a complex quality manifested in activity.

The problem of developing historical thinking has been addressed in the works of L.S. Vygotsky, Sh.A. Amonashvili, and A.V. Mudrik. According to these scholars, historical thinking is based on an individual's ability to comprehend social experience and analyze it logically.

Furthermore, the formation of personality based on historical and spiritual values is closely related to the axiological approach, which contributes to the development of a conscious and value-based attitude toward historical events.

Results And Discussion

The fundamental changes occurring in the modern education system, particularly the implementation of the competency-based approach, require updating the content of the pedagogical process. Today, the main objective of education is not limited to providing knowledge but also includes developing students' competencies in independent thinking, analysis, problem-solving, and decision-making.

From this perspective, in history education, the development of logical thinking alongside historical thinking is considered one of the key issues. In the process of training future history teachers, the formation of historical-logical competence is an important pedagogical task. This is because a history teacher acts not only as a transmitter of historical facts but also as a subject who develops students' historical consciousness, critical thinking, and analytical approach.

Historical-logical competence is defined as the ability of an individual to scientifically understand historical processes, identify cause-and-effect relationships between events, analyze historical facts, and draw logical conclusions.

Historical thinking refers to the ability of an individual to comprehend historical events and phenomena in terms of time, space, and causality. In this process, individuals not only remember past events but also analyze, compare, and generalize them.

Logical thinking, in turn, represents the ability to identify internal relationships between events, draw reasoned conclusions, and think based on evidence. As L.S. Vygotsky noted, the development of thinking is formed on the basis of social experience and deepens through logical operations.

Historical thinking and logical reasoning are closely interconnected and complement each other. Historical thinking is enriched through logical analysis, while logical reasoning develops based on historical material. Therefore, integrating these two processes increases the effectiveness of history education.

The integrative-modular approach serves as an important methodological basis for developing historical-logical competence. The integrative approach ensures interdisciplinary connections and promotes the comprehensive acquisition of knowledge. For example, integrating history with philosophy, sociology, geography, and cultural studies contributes to the formation of broad-based thinking among students.

The modular approach, in turn, divides the educational process into specific blocks, each aimed at developing particular competencies. This approach ensures the systematic and consistent organization of the educational process.

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